

ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

Digitization experts

Digital Tools, Monitoring Practices, and Data Acquisition

Digital Tools or Technologies

Digital Tools or Technologies used to Monitor

Data collected in Real Time

Challenges in Monitoring Workflows and Quality

Digitization experts

Data Types, Formats, and Interoperability Standards

Types of Data

Data Format

Standard or Protocols

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Data Accessibility, Sharing Practices, and Collaboration Platforms

Data Structure and Accessibility

Use of Collaborative Digital Platforms

Main Difficulties in Sharing Data

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3D Modelling, Digital Simulations, and Integration of Digital Technologies

Use of 3D Models

Use of Digital Simulation

Main Challenges in Integrating Digital Technologies

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Digital Twin Applications, Functional Expectations, and Future Adoption

Areas where Digital Twins are considered Most Useful

Information or Support expected from Reactive Digital Twins

Future Evolution of Digital Twin

ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

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Cross-analysis insights

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TECHNOLOGIES × DATA TYPES	2D image files (TIFF, JPEG, PNG, etc.)	Multispectral/hyperspectral image data	3D models (e.g., OBJ, PLY, glTF)	Raw sensor data (e.g., point clouds, reflectance spectra)	Technical metadata (e.g., EXIF, XMP, E57, XML)	Project documentation (e.g., condition reports, digitization protocols)	Linked metadata or authority files (e.g., VIAF, Wikidata, Getty AAT)	Geospatial data (e.g., GIS layers, coordinates)	Audio and video materials
2D high-resolution scanning	9	5	7	7	7	6	2	4	3
Multispectral or hyperspectral imaging	11	9	12	9	9	5	1	5	5
Photogrammetry tools	34	9	39	26	26	20	6	20	11
3D scanning tools (e.g., laser scanners, structured light)	31	9	40	26	25	20	6	18	13
Infrared or ultraviolet imaging	9	4	7	6	6	5	2	5	5
Digital microscopy	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	0	1
Image post-processing software (e.g., Adobe Photoshop, GIMP)	28	6	31	22	19	18	7	17	10
3D processing software (e.g., Agisoft Metashape, MeshLab, RealityCapture)	34	9	43	28	26	22	7	20	13
Workflow automation tools or scripts (e.g., Python, batch processing)	16	3	17	11	12	11	7	12	6
I am not directly involved in technical digitization	1	0	2	1	2	2	1	2	2

TECHNOLOGIES × REAL-TIME DATA	Data is acquired in real time or through automated systems (e.g., live sensor feeds, IoT devices)	Data is acquired periodically or in batches (e.g., scheduled digitization campaigns)	Data is acquired manually on demand	I'm not sure / Not applicable
2D high-resolution scanning	3	6	7	1
Multispectral or hyperspectral imaging	4	7	10	1
Photogrammetry tools	11	23	30	1
3D scanning tools (e.g., laser scanners, structured light)	13	23	27	1
Infrared or ultraviolet imaging	3	5	7	1
Digital microscopy	0	1	1	1
Image post-processing software (e.g., Adobe Photoshop, GIMP)	11	18	22	3
3D processing software (e.g., Agisoft Metashape, MeshLab, RealityCapture)	13	25	28	3
Workflow automation tools or scripts (e.g., Python, batch processing)	5	14	14	1
I am not directly involved in technical digitization	0	1	0	2

MONITORING TOOLS × MONITORING CHALLENGES	Lack of standardized quality control procedures	Limited time or staff resources for thorough review	Difficulties with file format compatibility and conversion	Metadata inconsistency or incompleteness	Insufficient tools for automated validation or monitoring	Poor integration between digitization and data management systems	No major difficulties
Quality control tools for digitized files	18	13	11	11	13	12	3
Metadata validation or auditing tools	13	11	8	11	12	9	0
File integrity monitoring systems	6	5	6	5	5	5	0
I do not use digital tools for monitoring	9	11	5	3	8	8	3

DATA TYPES × FORMATS	Standard image (TIFF, JPEG, PNG)	RAW image (e.g., DNG, proprietary RAW)	3D file formats or models (e.g., OBJ, STL, glTF, point clouds)	Audio/video (e.g., WAV, MP4)	Tabular data (e.g., CSV, Excel)	Structured metadata (e.g., XML, RDF, JSON)	Proprietary formats from specific software
2D image files (TIFF, JPEG, PNG, etc.)	35	20	37	12	20	11	19
Multispectral/hyperspectral image data	8	7	9	2	5	2	5
3D models (e.g., OBJ, PLY, glTF)	38	23	47	14	19	9	24
Raw sensor data (e.g., point clouds, reflectance spectra)	26	20	28	10	16	5	18
Technical metadata (e.g., EXIF, XMP, E57, XML)	26	14	27	7	18	9	16
Project documentation (e.g., condition reports, digitization protocols)	21	16	22	10	14	6	14
Linked metadata or authority files (e.g., VIAF, Wikidata, Getty AAT)	7	5	7	3	7	6	5
Geospatial data (e.g., GIS layers, coordinates)	21	11	22	8	17	8	13
Audio and video materials	15	10	16	14	7	4	8

COLLABORATIVE PLATFORMS × SHARING	Compatibility issues between different software and file formats	Legal or institutional restrictions on data sharing	Lack of adequate infrastructure for data storage and access	Concerns about intellectual property or data misuse	Incomplete or inconsistent metadata	Limited collaboration or communication with other institutions	I have no difficulties in sharing data
Yes, platforms	6	7	6	7	4	5	1
Yes, external or open-source platforms	3	5	7	3	3	5	0
No, but I'd be interested	15	12	15	9	11	10	2
No, I don't see their usefulness	1	1	1	1	0	2	0

3D MODELS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Lack of shared data models or interoperability standards	Fragmentation of workflows across teams or departments	Limited technical support or documentation	Difficulty aligning digitized outputs with archival or curatorial standards	Resistance to adopting new digital workflows	I don't experience major integration issues
Yes, frequently	20	20	15	16	16	6
Yes, occasionally	2	3	5	3	3	0
No, but I would be interested	1	1	1	2	0	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	0	0	0	0	0

3D MODELS × DIGITAL TWIN USE CASE	Visualization of heritage assets for public access or	Long-term preservation planning based on condition simulations	Integration of multimodal data (images, 3D, metadata, analytics)	Quality control and validation of digitization outputs	Reuse of digital content in new applications (e.g., AR/VR)	Enabling collaboration between institutions through shared digital models	I don't see relevant applications
Yes, frequently	31	34	31	18	22	28	0
Yes, occasionally	3	4	5	1	2	2	0
No, but I would be interested	1	1	1	1	1	2	0
No, and I don't see the	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

SIMULATIONS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Lack of shared data models or interoperability standards	Fragmentation of workflows across teams or departments	Limited technical support or documentation	Difficulty aligning digitized outputs with archival or curatorial standards	Resistance to adopting new digital workflows	I don't experience major integration issues
Yes, frequently	4	4	4	4	3	1
Yes, occasionally	7	10	7	8	6	2
No, but I would be interested	12	8	9	7	9	3
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	2	1	2	1	0

SIMULATIONS × REACTIVE DIGITAL TWIN	Centralized access to all digitized materials and metadata	Real-time environmental monitoring data from heritage sites	Version control and update tracking for digital records	Simulation of degradation or risk to digital or physical assets	Integration with external systems (e.g., archives, research infrastructures)	Interoperable models shared across institutions	Alerts and notifications for inconsistencies, errors or data gaps	I don't see how a Digital Twin would support my activities
Yes, frequently	5	5	5	5	6	5	5	0
Yes, occasionally	12	14	9	12	10	8	6	0
No, but I would be interested	15	13	11	12	11	13	9	2
No, and I don't see the	2	2	1	2	1	0	1	0